

TRAINING OF MANAGEMENT PERSONNEL IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This article presents an analysis of the training of management staff in higher education institutions based on innovative management. Relevant to any other area of management: goal setting and strategy selection, the four stages of the cycle are presented separately.

Keywords : innovation, management, , inspection, development, plan, leadership, control and analysis, experience, projects, decisions, news, efficiency, activity.

Based on previous studies recommending the introduction of a higher education data warehouse with a global change management approach, the integration of academic data in which universities in Europe and the United States can collaborate with not only public but also private universities you can learn that you need a system.

The company works to achieve its goals, one of which is to plan all resources used in business operations to create business, information systems and information technology strategies. Higher education institutions that use IPMS (Information Performance Management System) in their commercial operations always use all their available resources, especially IT and information system resources.

Higher education Information efficiency management system (IPMS) because he believes it will help him succeed in achieving his academic goals.

There are various reasons for using an information performance management system in higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan, but there are three main reasons:

- desire to achieve academic goals,
- The need to identify IT needs,
- IT benefits and not deploying information systems.

past experience or best practices of other universities, it is very important to use the information performance management system to realize the economic goals of higher education.

Problems existing in the management system of higher education institutions based on credit module technology can provide necessary material for the development of projects in various directions as an object for "oOfs registrar".

Office of the Registrar. In the current education system, many departments, such as deaneries, educational department, personnel department, admission department, deal with the contingent of students 72 credit module system and educational process organization. There is no centralized unit dealing with the student contingent. In the credit -module system, a centralized unit - the Registrar's Office deals with the contingent of students. His task is to draw up an academic calendar and control its timely execution, organize the work of the admissions committee, organize enrollment in subjects (Enrollment), form academic groups, organize and control the assessment of knowledge at the entrance, organize final control and intermediate attestations. conducting and conducting, organizing and supervising the conduct of the final state attestation, storing personal documents of students until the archive, forming and regularly updating the "Registrar" database, maintaining the transcript and including students' grades in it, organizing solemn ceremonies and o It will consist of tasks such as conducting (registration and ceremonial presentation of graduates' diplomas), keeping statistics on the student contingent. This structure is a student-oriented unit in the credit-module system,

which can be temporarily organized by attracting employees from the dean's office and departments until the full transition to the credit-module system.

Also, the further clarification of the areas of activity will provide material that will be the basis for new projects related to the specific nature of each educational area. In this regard, it is appropriate to take the following measures. Determining the object of research by identifying existing problems; identify project directions for pilot testing; approval of project groups, determination of their tasks; assigning to the established working groups the task of developing a new innovative project in a certain direction within a specified period; examination of proposed projects; development of the implementation program for each project, etc.

A mechanism for reforming the quality of training of management personnel of HEIs based on innovative management

The continuous evolution of the global educational field requires a corresponding increase in the quality of training of management personnel in higher education institutions. At a time when Uzbekistan is striving to strengthen its position in the world community, there is a need to introduce innovative management principles in the training of management personnel of HEIs.

In the course of the research, the researches and opinions of Uzbek scientists are studied, and the strategies that can help in this direction are clarified. With its rich history, the educational system of Uzbekistan has undergone many changes over the past few decades. The country's desire to reform the education system was clearly demonstrated in its efforts to introduce advanced world experience and innovative methodologies to the higher education sector. Alisher Umarov (2019) emphasizes the importance of modernizing curricula to keep up with modern global business and management paradigms. Opposing reliance on outdated teaching methodologies, he advocates

the use of real-time business problem solving, case studies and simulation exercises. Such pedagogical tools ensure that theoretical knowledge becomes practical. F. Madrahimova's (2020) research is about the digital revolution in pedagogy, and she draws inspiration from global trends and emphasizes that digital resources and e-learning modules can significantly enrich the quality of management training in HEIs of Uzbekistan. According to F. Madrahimova, the promotion of a mixed educational environment adapts the educational process to the demographic needs and preferences of modern students. B. Mukhtorov's research (2021) determines the need to form innovative thinking in the audience. He noted that while technical skills are essential in management, it is equally important to develop creativity, critical thinking and a penchant for innovation. A curriculum that supports these qualities, combined with industry partnerships, not only equips students to acquire knowledge, but also to develop leadership skills in them.

Research by N. Salimova (2018) shows the dynamic interaction between academic leadership and innovation management. A university's vision is greatly influenced by its leadership, and therefore it is important to prepare management staff to be skilled leaders in a changing educational environment. N. Salimova's work emphasizes that such training prepares leaders to effectively use opportunities and create active innovations. R. Joraev's (2019) studies of the

potential of public-private partnership shed light on the important aspect of improving the quality of management personnel training.

By establishing symbiotic relationships with the corporate world, HEIs not only ensure curriculum relevance but also provide students with real-world exposure. R. Joraev's emphasis on fostering entrepreneurial spirit through such partnerships resonates with the global shift toward industry-integrated education.

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